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**An Assessment Of Critical Community Needs In Developing Countries With Special
Reference To Southern Africa. The Case of Zambia (Shanty Compounds)**

(Participatory – (UN -DESA) Project/Msc-2022)

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Introduction

Nowadays they are a lot of debate as to whether community need assessment is important or vital to the development of the country needs and eradication of poverty among unprivileged people in these communities and the country in general. Therefore this united nation-Division for Social Policy and Development (DSPD) of the Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA) participatory project will try to critically identify 5 critical community needs with special reference to Kalingalinga compound.

Background of the Study

Kalingalinga is a low-income, high-density settlement. According to Ministry of Local Government And Housing-GRZ (2018) Kalingalinga compound population is estimated to be 115,000 this has been due to increase in the business activities by both small and medium enterprises. Kalingalinga is east-centrally located on the middle centre of the Lusaka province and surrounded by other communities like Mutendere, Kabulonga, Rhodespark, mass media, Hallen Kaunda and Kalundu (Ministry of Commerce-GRZ, 2016). According to Central statistics Office (2015) it can only take 15 kilometres from Lusaka international airport to Kalingalinga. Kalingalinga centre is usually characterized mainly by traders who sale different commodities ranging from hardware, automotive spare parts, restaurants, banking services, Movies, phones and second hand clothes and these businesses are usually run by entrepreneurs' usually young male and females.

The Research Problem

There has been a rise in the levels of population in Kalingalinga from 35,000 in 2012 to over 110,000 people as in 2018 and 60 percent of this population are unemployed youths (young aged male and female in their 20s) and because of this, crime rate has doubled in the last decade (Ministry of Education, 2021). Kalingalinga lacks proper sanitation and it became one of the communities that were heavily affected with cholera between 2008 and 2017 due to lack of safe and proper sanitations including drinking water. Kalingalinga Compounds, like other unplanned settlements in Lusaka, have experienced their share of adverse impacts arising from the weather-related events and mostly floods and this is due to poor drainage system and roads. Shortage of schools, medical facilities, business opportunity and proper council administration is one of the critical problems Kalingalinga is currently facing at the moment.

Literature Review

Zambia like any other developing countries in southern sub-Saharan Africa is still struggling in meeting community and country needs and one of the most significant features for Zambia in meeting community is high inequalities, which make the country very divided especially between urban and rural areas. As according to Mulenga (2003) Zambia ranks as one of the most unequal countries in the world. This does not only affect people living in poverty communities, but it is also a threat to long-term economic and social development of the country. Therefore, reducing inequalities in redistribution of community need is important both in economic terms, as well as in choices and opportunities, in social services, and between rural and urban areas, as well as between men and women. When looking at inequalities in distribution of need within communities especially in Lusaka province, it is apparent that there is a distinct relationship between levels of education and levels of poverty all comes to basic community needs. As Aaron (2008) noted that, many of the poor people in these communities in southern Africa are working in the informal sector, mostly in the agricultural sector or in small business. The majority of the people in Zambia are in the informal sector are classified as poor working and have little or no access to social security or better accommodation (LCC, 2008). Their daily life situation is very unstable and they are facing many sorts of community risk. They have difficulties to improve and expand their business due to lack of capital and low productivity. On the other side, Bruce and Brandon (2017) observed in his article on assessing community need is that lack of proper council and better healthcare policy to benefit the poor in these communities is one of the biggest challenges when it comes to community needs. Zambia has legal restrictions on how many council offices each community will have and no restrictions on better healthcare hospitals or clinics but the only problem they are more applied to the formal sector especially to upper class or high income communities which has been the major problem.

Data Collection Methodology

Study employed the use of exploratory research design. The research study area was Kalingalinga compound in Lusaka district. The study used a structured questionnaire for interviews with respondents (Cook, 1997; Chambers, 1994). Secondary data was gathered through secondary information such as published articles, local government ministry and online research papers. A Non-probability Sampling Technique. That was convenience sampling was employed in this research. A sample size of 30 was drawn from the population of 115,000 Kalingalinga residents. Descriptive statistical techniques including mean scores were used to assess the importance of each factor given by students. Both Excel and SPSS were used to analyze the data.

Results Discussions

Response Rate

Based on the survey information gathered in kalingalinga compound, it can be observed through table 1.0 that the research questionnaires response rate was 71% questionnaires were issued to a total respondents of 28 kalingalinga compound residents and only 20 questionnaires were returned and 8 questionnaires were discarded. As Mokhlis (2009) asserted that, the response rate of over 70 per cent is considered sufficient for statistically reliability and generalization.

Sex and Age of the Respondents Results

A summary of results on kalingaling residents' on demography profile along three variables that is sex and age of the respondent has been presented in table 3.0. The results show that out of 20 respondents, N=12 (60%) were males and the remaining N=8 (40%) were female. Results on respondents' age shows that N=13(65) were between the age of 18 and 25 years of age and N=7 (35%) were between the age of 26 and 35 years of age. The researcher didn't record any respondents of 36 age or more from the overall received questionnaires as shown in table 2.0.

Levels of education

A summary of results on kalingalinga residents' levels of education presented in table 4.0, shows that out of 20 respondents, N= 10 (50%) had only a grade 12 certificate and N=10 (50%) had a diploma respectively. No student was recorded to have a bachelor's degree, Master degree or even a PhD and N=0 (0 per cent) was recorded to these groups respectively.

Employment status and Monthly Income of the Respondents Results

The summary of results as indicated in table 5.0 below shows that, out of 20 respondents, N= 10 (50%) of the respondents are unemployed, followed by N= 5 (25%) of the respondents are Self-employed and N=5 (25 per cent) of the respondents are on part-time job and N=0 (0%) of the respondents are Permanent full-time job. On monthly income, the results obtained showed that most respondents had monthly earnings of K2000 or less N=10 (50%) and between K3, 000 and K8, 000 was N= 10 (50%).

Explanation of Ranked Critical Community Need Assessment Factors Results

An in-depth explanation based on the observation from the rotated factor matrix table 2.0 as follows: The twelve (12) factors were ranked according to their respective mean values and, the top six (6) critical community needs that were considered the most by the respondents were as follows: House/household, Education-Schools, Food, Hospitals, Clean Water and Sanitation and more employment opportunities. It is worth to note that, similar studies found that most compound residents in Zambia attached the same importance to the county needs listed above. In the study by Aaron (2018); Gerrard and Cunningham (2001); Patrick, (2001) clearly shows that household was ranked highest compared to Schools, Food and clean water. This is an indication that most kalingalinga compound residents want to associate themselves with these top six critical community needs. Moreover, on the researcher's side, the result still remains surprising as some major critical community needs such as more Police Post, Roads and Proper Drainage Systems and an Effective Community Council scored low among other critical community needs. Therefore, we cannot assume these results to be the same

with critical community needs assessment process employed in developed countries such as the United States, United Kingdom, German, China or Japan.

Critical Community Needs Matrix of Institutional Listing and Ranking in Kalingalinga Compound from Institutional Mapping.

The Church-From the survey results, the kalingalinga compound respondents were asked if they consider the church very important or very least important in County Needs Matrix of Institutional mapping. Out of the total respondents of 20, N=10 (50%) consider the church very important, followed by N= 5 (25%) consider it to be important and N=3 (15%) were neutral and lastly, N=2 (10%) consider it to be of very least important as indicated in table 6.0.

Lusaka City Council (LCC)-From the survey results, the kalingalinga compound respondents were asked if they consider Lusaka City Council very important or very least important in community needs assessments. Out of the total respondents of 20, N=13 (65%) consider Lusaka City Council very important, followed by N= 7 (35%) consider it to be important as indicated in table 6.0.

NGOs- From the survey results, the kalingalinga compound respondents were asked if they consider NGOs very important or very least important in the County Needs Matrix of institutional mapping. Out of the total respondents of 20, N=6 (30%) consider NGOs very important, followed by N= 10 (50%) consider it to be important and N=3 (15%) were neutral and lastly, N=1 (5%) consider it to be of very least important as indicated in table 6.0.

Ward Development and Committee (WDC) - From the survey results, the kalingalinga compound respondents were asked if they consider Ward Development and Committee very important or very least important in the County Needs Matrix of institutional mapping. Out of the total respondents of 20, N=15 (75%) consider Ward Development and Committee very important, followed by N= 5 (25%) consider it to be important as indicated in table 6.0.

Explanation of the Results of Critical Community Needs Matrix of Institutional Listing and Ranking in Kalingalinga Compound from Institutional Mapping.

From the views expressed by different respondents, we can argue that the ward development and committee and Lusaka City Council are very important to almost all of the respondents. These needs may not be very visible to outsiders communities like Mtendere and Kalikiliki because of the differences in demography and levels of population. Part of the reason for this having these results, arises from the fact that the highly needs of institutions in communities, as Peter (2019) observed that on the urban communities are gradual and almost insidious i.e. difficult to observe compared to rural communities needs. But Kings (2020) argued that rural community needs are just the same with those in the urban communities. For example according to the survey by Riche (2007) noted that, in Zambia city councils and ward development are considered to be important because of political influence they have through decentralization.

Similar views or actions were argued across all respondents groups with business asset adaptation measures. Two men, for example, both aged between 30 and 40 years, and owing a business in kalingalinga Compound asserted that NGOs and Churches are equally important institutions as they have supported SMEs and unprivileged children's in kalingalinga when councils and the government in general are not able to do so.

Recommendations

The following are the critical recommendation on critical community needs assessment based on the data results and the study in general:

- i. The government and other developmental institutions should take a keen interest in understanding and providing the critical community needs such as schools, healthcare, proper roads and sanitations.
- ii. Non-Governmental organizations and the government through the ministry of community and development and the local councils should start conducting critical needs assessment at least every year to best understand and address community need.

Summary

In summary, the project has managed to answer the project question.

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